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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the results of assessing the factor of safety “K” of the earth fill dam at the Kizilsay reservoir. The study considers two structural configurations of the dam: an inclined-core dam and a central-core dam. The computational cases include the effect of the dam’s self-weight alone, as well as the combined effect of self-weight and hydrostatic pressure at a water depth of $H_{\text{water}}=80\text{m}$. The obtained results show that, in both configurations, the condition $K > 1$ is satisfied in potentially critical zones. Under the effect of self-weight, the factor of safety in certain zones of the inclined-core dam is 13–20% higher than that of the central-core configuration. Under hydrostatic pressure, the stress state in the upstream prism is redistributed, resulting in a noticeable increase in the value of “K” in the inclined-core dam. At the same time, these results should be interpreted with caution, since soil wetting and seepage pressure were not taken into account in the present computational case.

Keywords: Kizilsay reservoir, earth fill dam, inclined core, central core, hydrostatic pressure, factor of safety, stress state, stability.

Introduction

Reservoirs and earth fill dams are important hydraulic engineering structures that ensure water management, irrigation, energy supply, and public safety. During long-term operation, such structures are subjected to multiple interacting factors, including self-weight, water pressure, seepage, seismic effects, temperature variations, and time-dependent changes in material properties. Therefore, the computational assessment of the strength and stability of earth fill dams remains a relevant issue not only at the design stage but also during operation [1; 2].

In earth fill dams, critical zones usually form along the upstream and downstream slopes, at the interfaces between the core and the prisms, in the contact zones with the foundation, and in geometric transition areas where stress concentrations occur. Determining the local values of the factor of safety in such zones is essential for evaluating the overall reliability of the dam. This issue becomes particularly important under high reservoir water levels, where hydrostatic pressure affects the horizontal normal stresses within the dam body and leads to the redistribution of strength parameters.

A comparative analysis of two structural schemes of the earth fill dam at the Kizilsay Reservoir — namely, the inclined-core and central-core configurations — is of practical importance. The location of the core directly affects the impervious function of the dam, the distribution of stresses, the compaction state of the upstream prism, and slope stability. From this perspective, the present article discusses the distribution of the factor of safety “K” under the effects of the dam’s self-weight and hydrostatic pressure.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study is to assess the distribution of the factor of safety in the inclined-core and central-core configurations of the earth fill dam at the Kizilsay Reservoir and to determine the characteristics of its variation under the effect of hydrostatic pressure.

To achieve this purpose, the following objectives were defined:

to compare the two structural configurations of the dam from a computational point of view; to analyze the distribution of the factor of safety “K” under the effect of self-weight; to evaluate the redistribution of the stress state under hydrostatic pressure at a water depth of $H_{\text{water}}= 80 \text{ m}$; to provide an engineering interpretation of the influence of inclined and central core arrangements on the factor of safety; and to summarize the computational results from the standpoint of operational safety.

Computational approach and methodology

The factor of safety “K” was adopted as the main indicator for assessing the strength condition of the earth fill dam. In general engineering interpretation, this coefficient expresses the ratio between the soil’s resistance capacity and the actual stress state developing within the structure. If $K > 1$ the strength condition at the considered computational point is regarded as satisfied. The greater the value of K, the higher the safety margin at that point. Conversely, as K approaches 1, the probability of a potentially critical zone increases [3; 4].

For soils, such an assessment depends on shear resistance, the angle of internal friction, cohesion, normal stresses, and the calculated shear stresses. In practice, the factor of safety is often interpreted as the ratio between the limiting shear resistance and the actual shear stress. Therefore, isolines of the coefficient “K” represent a convenient graphical result, indicating which areas of the dam body have a higher safety margin and which areas have a comparatively lower one. [3; 4].

Two main computational cases were considered in the study. In the first case, only the effect of the dam body’s self-weight was taken into account. This case makes it possible to assess the factor of safety of the dam under dry or initial static operating conditions, without the influence of water. In the second case, the hydrostatic pressure generated by the reservoir was considered together with the dam’s self-weight. The water depth was assumed to be $H_{\text{water}}= 80 \text{ m}$ and the pressure was applied to the upstream prism as a horizontal load increasing with depth[5].

The main feature of hydrostatic pressure is that it acts along the upstream slope in contact with water and increases with depth. This pressure interacts with the horizontal normal stresses within the dam body and may increase compressive stresses in certain zones. Since the shear resistance of soil depends on the normal stress, an increase in compressive normal stresses may lead to an increase in the calculated factor of safety. However, this conclusion is valid only for the case where soil wetting, pore water pressure, and seepage effects are not considered [1; 7].

Assessment of strength under the effect of self-weight

Self-weight forms the initial field of vertical and horizontal stresses within the dam body. In earth fill dams, this effect is distributed differently depending on the geometry of the structure, slope angles, the position of the core, material density, and interaction with the foundation. Since the spatial arrangement of the core differs in the inclined-core and central-core configurations, the internal stresses are also not distributed identically.

According to the analysis results, under the effect of self-weight alone, the values of the factor of safety “K” exceed 1.5 in the main part of the dam in both structural configurations. This indicates that the dam

has a sufficient general strength reserve under static gravitational loading. The condition $K > 1$ is also satisfied in the upper part, along the slopes, and in the transition zones between the prism and the core, which may be considered potentially critical areas.

The comparative analysis shows that, in the inclined-core dam configuration, the coefficient “K” in the upstream prism and in some zones of the downstream slope is generally 13–20% higher than that of the central-core configuration. This result can be explained by the more favorable redistribution of stresses within the dam body due to the inclined core. In other words, the inclined core, through its interaction with the upstream prism, reduces certain horizontal and shear stresses and thereby increases the stability reserve of the dam.

In the central-core configuration, the core is located close to the symmetry axis of the dam; therefore, the redistribution of stresses in the upstream prism is less pronounced than in the inclined-core configuration. This does not mean that the central-core dam is unsafe, since the condition $K > 1$ is also satisfied in this case. However, from the standpoint of the factor of safety, the inclined-core configuration may be considered more advantageous in certain zones.

Figure 1. Distribution isolines of the factor of safety “K” in the Kizilsay earthfill dam under the effect of self-weight: a) inclined-core dam; b) central-core dam.

Assessment of strength under the combined effect of self-weight and hydrostatic pressure

In the second computational case, hydrostatic pressure was added to the self-weight of the dam. At a water level of $H_{\text{water}}=80\text{m}$, the pressure acting along the upstream slope significantly changes the stress state within the dam body. In this case, the horizontal component of pressure compresses the upstream prism to a certain extent and thereby affects the field of normal stresses.

According to the analysis results, the distribution of the coefficient “K” is reshaped under the effect of hydrostatic pressure. In particular, in the upstream prism of the inclined-core dam, the factor of safety increases by up to 2–3 times. This is explained by the transition of the upstream prism into a more compressed stress state under hydrostatic loading, which increases the soil’s resistance to shear. In soils, when normal compressive stress increases, the shear resistance potential also increases due to internal friction.

In the central-core configuration, redistribution of the coefficient “K” under hydrostatic pressure is also observed; however, the degree of increase is lower than in the inclined-core dam. This difference is associated with the geometric location of the core, which is relatively farther from the upstream prism or positioned differently within the dam body. The inclined core redistributes the pressure effect within the structure more effectively and, as a result, increases the factor of safety in certain zones.

This result must be interpreted carefully from an engineering point of view. The calculations did not ac-

count for soil wetting, seepage flow, pore water pressure, or deterioration of material properties under the effect of water. Under real operating conditions, water acts not only as external hydrostatic pressure but also generates seepage processes inside the dam body. Seepage pressure and wetting may reduce the effective stresses of the soil and negatively affect cohesion and internal friction parameters. Therefore, the “positive” effect of hydrostatic pressure in this computational case is explained only from the viewpoint of the compressive action of external pressure; it cannot replace a complete hydrogeomechanical analysis.

a)

b)

Figure 2. Distribution isolines of the factor of safety “K” in the Kizilsay earthfill dam under the combined effect of self-weight and hydrostatic pressure ($H_{water} = 80\text{ m}$): a) inclined-core dam; b) central-core dam.

Comparative analysis of the results

The comparison of the inclined-core and central-core configurations shows that the position of the core within the dam structure has a significant influence on the distribution of the factor of safety. Under the effect of self-weight, the higher safety reserve in the upstream prism and downstream slope zone of the inclined-core configuration indicates that the core acts as an element that redirects the internal stress field. When hydrostatic

pressure is added, this difference becomes even more pronounced.

The table below summarizes the main engineering conclusions for the considered computational cases. As can be seen from the table, although both configurations satisfy the safety condition, the inclined-core dam has a higher factor of safety in certain zones. This allows it to be considered a preferable solution from the standpoint of operational safety.

Table 1.

Comparative assessment of the strength condition of the Kizilsay earthfill dam configurations

Computational case	Inclined-core dam	Central-core dam	Engineering interpretation
Self-weight	$K > 1.5$; relatively higher safety margin in the upstream prism	$K > 1.5$; stable condition is ensured	The static strength condition is satisfied in both configurations
Slope and downstream zones	In some areas, K is 13–20% higher	A safety margin exists, but it is lower than in the inclined-core configuration	The inclined core redistributes stresses more favorably
Self-weight + hydrostatic pressure	In the upstream prism, K may increase by up to 2–3 times	K is redistributed, but the degree of increase is lower	External water pressure increases compressive normal stresses
Limitation	Wetting and seepage were not considered	Wetting and seepage were not considered	A complete assessment requires seepage and seismic analyses

Scientific and practical significance

The results of the study are of practical importance for comparing structural configurations of the Kizilsay dam. By analyzing the isolines of the factor of safety, it is possible to identify relatively critical and relatively safe zones within the dam body. This is useful for selecting monitoring points, determining additional strengthening measures, improving the computational model, and increasing operational safety.

From a scientific perspective, the obtained results demonstrate the influence of core position on the stress–strain state of an earth fill dam. The inclined core may be considered not only as an impervious element but also as a structural factor that redistributes stresses within the dam body. This indicates that, when designing earth fill dams, the selection of core geometry should be approached not only from the viewpoint of impermeability but also from the standpoint of strength and stability.

At the same time, this analysis serves as a basis for further research. At the next stages, it would be appropriate to perform comprehensive calculations that include wetting, the seepage field, pore water pressure, seismic effects, and hydrodynamic pressure. Such an approach would make it possible to obtain an assessment that is closer to the real operating conditions of the dam.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of the inclined-core and central-core configurations of the earth fill dam at the Kizilsay reservoir, the following conclusions can be formulated.

First, under the effect of self-weight alone, the factor of safety “K” exceeds 1.5 in the main zones of the dam in both structural configurations, and the condition $K > 1$ is satisfied in potentially critical zones. This indicates that the dam has a sufficient overall safety margin under static gravitational loading.

Second, in the inclined-core dam, the factor of safety in some zones of the upstream prism and downstream slope is approximately 13–20% higher than that of the central-core dam. This demonstrates that the inclined core contributes to a more favorable redistribution of stresses and increases the stability reserve.

Third, when hydrostatic pressure corresponding to a water depth of $H_{\text{water}}=80$ m is added, redistribution of the coefficient “K” is observed within the dam body. In the upstream prism of the inclined-core configuration, the value of “K” increases by up to 2–3 times, which is explained by the formation of compressive horizontal stresses caused by external water pressure.

Fourth, the conclusion regarding the positive effect of hydrostatic pressure is valid only for the case where soil wetting, seepage flow, and pore water pressure are not considered. Under real operating conditions, a complete safety assessment requires the combined performance of seepage, deformation, and seismic analyses.

In general, the inclined-core structural scheme provides relatively favorable results in certain zones of the Kizilsay earth fill dam in terms of the factor of safety. Therefore, this configuration may be considered one of the priority options for further comprehensive analyses and for evaluating operational safety.

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